

NIETZSCHE'S EXISTENTIALIST PHILOSOPHY EXPRESSED IN BATMAN'S SOCIOPATHIC BEHAVIOR: PARADOXAL STATEMENTS ABOUT HOPE

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the presence of Nietzsche's philosophy in Batman, expressed through his sociopathic and, at times, misunderstood behavior. The target object that permeates this discussion is hope, in which Nietzsche and the Guardian of Gotham consider it as the worst of all evils; since it prolongs man's suffering and, in this, both fight against it, characterizing it as a terrible monster and, the most interesting thing was that they ended up becoming symbols of hope: the Philosopher becomes the destiny of Philosophy, the his last lifeline and the Detective, becomes the fate of Gotham City, also his last lifeline. This work is the result of the analysis and interpretation of the short film *Dying is Very Easy*, released in 2021, in which Batman is taken to the extreme of his perspicacity, in order to solve a crime committed by the Joker and which ended up being transformed by the Rascal-Clown into a child's game against the police and authorities. Discourse analysis and content analysis were used as instruments of hermeneutic interpretation, in addition to knowledge of Psychoanalysis to reach an understanding of the thoughts exposed by the author in the work studied. Two of Nietzsche's aphorisms were taken and, consequently, the two books where the cited texts are exposed, in order to clarify the discussion. Frederico Nietzsche's philosophy is placed as the leitmotif of a cinematographic work featuring two epic rivals as protagonists and the result was the best philosophical representation of human existence.

Keywords: Nietzsche; Batman; Hope; Hopelessness; Joker.

INTRODUCTION

In 1878, Friedrich Nietzsche (1844-1900) wrote that, "hope is the worst of all evils; therefore, it prolongs the suffering of men" (Id., 2006, p. 83). He adds that this was Zeus' true revenge against men; the father of the gods wanted humans not to abandon life, even though they were tortured in every way imaginable by various evils.

It turns out that there is a type of torture imposed by hope that becomes the cruelest of all, which causes individuals not to move forward with their lives towards the future, not to mourn their losses, because they are trapped by feelings that these did not actually occur and that a miracle could still happen; it is the expectation that their missing loved ones will still return to their homes and families.

In the creation of Christianity, this was the main flag defended and which ended up becoming a condition of *love towards others* (*in fact, it could not be anything else*), that of keeping hope alive until the individual could no longer bear all the suffering. suffering, becoming alienated to feelings, things, people and causes that, if overcome, would give them dignified living conditions and free from incessant pain.

For the first time, a film explores Nietzsche's philosophy and psychology without doing any rhetorical juggling to adapt the master's thought to a society that cannot bear to be confronted with the reality of its existence. As always, the Guardian of Gotham City, being one step ahead of everyone, goes in search of a resolution to a case already considered solved in his sociopathic mind; However, there was the problem that the location of the bodies of the missing police officers had not been known for 3 (three) months.

In order to definitively solve the case, Batman begins a heavy and risk-filled game with the Clown Prince of Crime, the Joker, who is trapped in Arkham Asylum, after one of his usual escapes. He takes Bat to the extreme of his madness and pain, bringing to the Hero's memory two emblematic cases that Bruce was unable to succeed in: the shattered spine of Bárbara Gordon, Batgirl who now works to combat the crime as Oracle; and, the impulsive Jason Todd, the 2nd Robin who returns to life, taking on the mantle of the Red Hood, ironically, the disguise that the Joker wore the day he dives into the acid tank, in an attempt to escape the pursuit of the one who would come to become your greatest friend and your only true passion.

Batman, better than anyone, knows the thoughts of the Rascal Clown and knows very well that he will try to take him to his extreme, because however strange the expression may seem, the Joker is a classic man, a warrior created along the lines of virtue and ancient thought, in which death must be honorable and the life of someone like him, taken by a true champion, a being worthy of doing it, as if the last memories recorded by the condemned were that of someone he loves and respect above all. It's this psychological game, which the Clown Prince of Crime knows like no one else, given that all his victims called for someone who represented strength and power in the final moments of their miserable existences, and with Jason it couldn't have been any different. It turns out that with Jason Todd it was different; he did not invoke his master's name at the time of his death and this upset the Clown. Catherine Todd (the biological

mother of the 2nd Robin) told Bat the final moments of her son, who had died like a samurai warrior, with honor, trying to defend her from the inevitable.

What the Joker tries to do is make Batman understand that he does not represent hope for Gotham City and its inhabitants, much less for his companions on the epic journey. Sacripanta's mistake was to believe that this is a feeling that the Guardian feeds; on the contrary, it is what fights at all times, acting in an attempt to satisfy the desires of ordinary individuals; those that everyone directs, in deep and absolute silence, to some supernatural force and which only reveals itself through sighs. And he is this invisible force that listens to them in the midst of the densest darkness.

NIETZSCHE, BATMAN AND HOPE

Nietzsche and Batman have one thing in common, they both fight against hope, considering it as the *root cause* of all the greatest human torments. However, there is no way to fight a monster without ending up absorbed by its most powerful characteristic, the subjective force it exerts on everyone and, in 1886, the professor from Basel Switzerland had already written something along these lines in which he warned: "He who fights against monsters you must be careful so that in the process you do not also become a monster. When you look into the abyss for a long time, the abyss looks back into you" (NIETZSCHE, 2006, p. 89). "And, as if it were possible to complement the sentence above, I would say that the abyss, in addition to looking at you, can end up hypnotizing and swallowing you, absorbing and nullifying you" (SCHWAN, 2018, p. 1).

What did Nietzsche want to reveal with this aphoristic expression? What monster are you talking about? What abyss are you talking about? This is one of the most striking points in understanding the thoughts of the two characters in this article: when they both looked into the abyss, what they expected to see is a revelation for their questions and, when the abyss looks back at them, looking into their worlds, instead of granting them what they want, imposes a sentence on them; perhaps the most terrible thing anyone can receive: "Become what you are!" And so the pastor becomes crazy? No, he becomes a philosopher and the playboy billionaire becomes a monster? No way; becomes the most human individual that Clark could find among humans. Nietzsche had already said that he was a destiny (2006) and, in the same way, Batman also becomes a destiny; the fate of Gotham City. It was no surprise that he gained the trust of the city's highest police authority and, later, even Amanda Waller, figures who represented the micro and macro universe of politics.

Both characters know that hope is a monster and its existence reveals an insurmountable abyss, precisely because it feeds the lack of an element that completes the journey and even makes it represent any meaning. In a very strange, paradoxical way, so to speak, the philosopher and the Watcher have become what they challenge their existence against: symbols of hope! Batman is tortured and crushed by the expectation of finding his parents' killer and bringing him to justice and, much more, understanding why he took the lives of 2 (two) illustrious Gothamite citizens.

Once again there is the presence of Nietzsche's philosophy in Batman's life, because what did the apparently meaningless death of his parents seek to keep hidden from his eyes? What truths are hidden behind this crime that has not been solved, despite the apparent efforts of the Gotham Police? Bruce began to interpret the ineptitude of the police as a bureaucratic effect of the crime and that, if two well-presented figures of society end up in the common grave of legal-sociological equality in police records and bulletins, the common human being has nothing left but of an existence marked by emptiness and fear.

Here, Bruce becomes a symbol of hope for these individuals, disguised as a crime fighter, awakening terror in criminals who hide in the shadows to commit evil and violence. At no point in his life did he want to be this monster represented in the figure of a nocturnal and predatory animal. But, over time, the people of Gotham began to sleep more peacefully; because, on the highest towers of their city and under the always leaden sky of Gotham City, a god guarded them and even the Commissioner of Police, James Gordon, came to see in Batman a form of hope that he could not find in the authorities of your city and in your body of members. Harvey Dent, the prosecutor who transforms into the villain Two-Face, came to see the Hero as the only form of hope for justice in the *City of Goats*.

It is unknown to what extent its Guardian could be held responsible for the madness that had taken over the city, with lunatics of all types emerging from the shadows and terrorizing everyone. And, what was most frightening was the fact that, the more they expanded, the more these iconic figures from the criminal underworld made it seen as a symbol of hope; the monster of darkness transformed into the monster of light, making it an idol to be respected and admired in the same proportion as one should hate it, because it did not simply reveal evils; he was the revelation of the evil that lived in the unconscious of each member of his team.

The principles that guide Batman's journey are unknown, leading everyone and, more especially, the Joker to doubt that his friend sees any sense in his fight, precisely because he cannot save his friends from death or fateful ends, all caused by he, the king of chaos. It is at this point that the Sacripanta Clown is wrong about his rival and demonstrates that he judges

him based on common sense values, because the Bat knows that, no matter how hard he tries, failure is part of his life, as a hero; However, there is something it can do perfectly, which is to investigate and clarify the facts that led to the deaths of some people and provide a *sui generis* type of comfort to families, knowing the reason why their loved ones were killed.

In a normal head, like that of the Joker and the Gotham police officers, none of this can make any sense; but, in the final scene of the short film *Dying is Very Easy* (2021) , Bruce explains to Sergeant Bullock the reason for his journey and his commitment to bringing a fair and enlightened end to the crimes he faces in his city. As a social psychologist, he understood well the private feeling towards loved ones and how individuals form bonds of love and brotherhood with their closest ones.

BATMAN: DYING IS VERY EASY

This is a short film in which the Gotham police are searching for 3 (three) missing police officers and, as is only natural, the greatest detective in the world also enters the scene in order to solve the case. In a raid, to save a child from the Mad Hatter, Batman finds evidence that could lead him to a possible solution to the problem. Almost 3 (three) months later, the Joker sends a message to the Dark Knight that he wants to see him at Arkham, which is now under the direction of Hugo Strange, the psychopathic psychiatrist.

Right away, the Clown laments the immense sadness he feels at having to die there, from a common disease, like an ordinary man, after having lived as a legend, a demigod, lost in the heights of madness and fear. It wasn't honorable for everything to end like this... and, when Batman ignores him, threatening to leave, he begins his game of provocations, awakening old legends and accusing the Detective of being the true curse for Gotham, in which half of the tombstones in Cemeteries are marks of the Hero's action, that is, he does not represent hope for the Gothamite people, but rather their misfortune. Joker tells Batman that he doesn't kill him, it's not because of a moral code; it's out of fear: "Without me, you can't justify your existence! I'm the only thing you're not. You've spent your whole life fighting crime, night after night; dead partner after dead partner; and so you, Little Bat, are completely unhappy. You are scared of something that could bring you joy. (...) I absolutely love my life, but you absolutely hate yours" (CORINGA, 2021, sp).

Batman enters the game and says that the Joker is nothing and that there is no one to fill his always empty spirit; everyone else has someone or something to worry about and thus make their existence count. "How long has it been since it's been in the newspapers?" He questions

Batman and it is at this moment, in order to justify his power that he reveals the murder of the missing police officers and the place where they are hiding.

Batman created an entire apparatus of real provocation, with the intention of convincing everyone of the Joker's illness and his terminal condition, because he knew that before the end, he would call him to a meeting and end up being betrayed by his immense pride. But, “what does this mean? Why did you do all this for them?” asks Sergeant Bullock. Batman answers him, categorically: “I didn't do it for them, but for their families. I took away their hope so they could heal. I was told that the worst thing to come was Pandora's Box, not the sadness and the plagues; even hope... hope is a bet, it lacks certainties and this city knows very well what hopelessness and pain can do... drive you crazy! Without hope, families can heal and move forward.”

Bullock says that, from this moment on, he understands why Gordon respects him. In a monologue, Bruce reveals, “Bullock was right to call me a denizen of madness. Not knowing why or who killed my parents left me with this open wound. An abyss that I look into every night and all of this has made me a monster... a monster that I fear and embrace... a monster called Batman!”

Batman plays a very strange play on words in which he puts *hope* and *hopelessness* in the same period and, what most attracts attention is that his interlocutor understands well what he is expressing. The experience lived for years, living in the Grotesque City and witnessing all types of insanity allowed the Sergeant to interpret the Detective's expressed thoughts, without hesitation. When he says that hope is *a bet* and, paradoxically, that *it lacks certainties*, he is revealing the conflict that forms in the spirit of those who hope... On the one hand, the one who waits for a miracle needs to believe in luck and the one who promises the solution, through logic, is seen to be on the verge of guaranteeing the event. And, when he talks about hopelessness, it is about the phenomenon of loss of faith in authorities and their promises, causing them to seek, on their own, tortuous paths that do not lead to a happy ending.

Hopelessness, or in the classical semantic sense, ceasing to have hope because of disappointment, becomes the abyss that Nietzsche alluded to, and the more one looks into it, the more it returns this gaze, marked by violence and despair until that there is no place left where one can take refuge other than madness. There was something that Bruce knew as well as anyone else and, when reading the works of the German philosopher, he found answers to what came and went in his thoughts, at the same time that he found meaning in his endeavor, saving the inhabitants of his city, not the madness itself; but the worst of all the evils that haunt humanity and that are sold on every street corner: *Hope*.

At no point does it state that it seeks to take away the hope of existence from the citizens of Gotham; it only seeks to save them from situations in which maintaining hope causes more pain and anguish than the explicit truth. Bullock was wrong in his analysis when he said that Batman was not crazy; yes, he is and, moreover, contrary to what can be understood, he knows the paths that led him to the state of madness; For this reason, it can interfere precisely, preventing its development in others.

CONCLUSION

Batman tells the Joker that dying is not easy, in contrast to the Clown's speech, and he is right; because, it is not about deciding to die; We have to face the mysterious dilemma of the unknown that death guards with so much zeal and affection. What man does not know, he tends to fear and, in relation to death, it could not be otherwise. It becomes, every day, an abyss that you avoid looking at, which leads you to feed hope, through plans for a future that is limited along with your existence; This is a condition you prefer to ignore. So, it's not about looking in the opposite direction of the abyss; there must be something to look at, even if it is a haunting evil that consumes his spirit, transforming him into a drunken dreamer or a mad sadist, in the end.

Nietzsche and Batman created their own doctrines with the purpose of fighting a monster that could not be defeated and, strangely, in an enigmatic way, they overcame it; however, the price they were forced to pay was with the mission of taking the place of this being they defeated. This is the meaning of defeating a supernatural force, an idol, in which the masses, without anything to place as a legitimate and immediate substitute, elect the one who defeated them as the one who should be worshiped and give thanks and supplications to him, in moments of joy and of anguish, respectively.

The Philosopher and the Watcher have many similarities; Both are detectives, in their respective ways, but they lived in search of the truth, without caring about the pain this could cause. They lost their father very early. The first started fighting a mysterious illness, hoping to find a cure, until he had to admit that his illness was incurable. Bruce, likewise, recognizes that the mystery surrounding his parents' death is insoluble and what challenges him, from this moment on, is the reason for all the ineptitude of Gotham's justice system.

Both ended up destroyed, emotionally, when they were faced with hopelessness and madness was the abyss that absorbed them in a more pragmatic way. Contrary to what one might consider, neither Nietzsche nor Batman desire the death of hope; What they seek is the

human power to go beyond what oppresses them and thus overcome the obstacles that eventually arise abruptly.

The Dark Knight, disciplined through Eastern doctrine, knew well the respect that humans have for the dead and the responsibility of offering them an honorable and dignified funeral, allowing their spirits to rest in peace. Likewise, the Gotham Police felt the need to pay their respects to their battle brothers; a rite of passage that raises the spirit of the corporation, even though this can be a time of pain and suffering.

Bruce has always had a lot of respect for the Joker, despite all the differences they have; but, waking up with a huge smile on his face, precisely because of the psychological suffering caused to the families of the dead police officers and the police force and, even worse, the pain and humiliation caused to his great friend James Gordon, made him feel repulsed by that clown . If he, the Bat, was the target in question, this made him play with all the dirty chips he had to get to the end of the matter and solve the case; He had delved deeper than he thought he could bear into his own abyss, just to find the answer he wanted. I didn't imagine that it was a sadistic game designed with the purpose of having fun while mocking everyone, awakening terror in the population, destroying the meager hope that citizens placed in their police and their guardian.

In the same way as Batman, when the Joker is forced to look into the abyss and it returns his gaze, imposing a sentence on him, he takes it in its crudest sense, trying to laugh at everything that had happened to him and so he it makes something no human can deal with, super sanity; the extemporaneous expression of the chaos that is hidden in reality, someone who lives without any kind of hope, using the phenomenological characterization of existence to elaborate their actions. Joker is the maximum expression of hopelessness and also its most palpable effect.

Batman does not propose the destruction of hope in life; his purpose is to destroy that which fixates on a single thing, ignoring the constant phenomenological aspect of existence, in which authorities and even ordinary people or someone like him, who acts from the shadows, fight so that everyone can continue to have hope.

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